

European Career Framework

**Eurodoc position paper and
recommendations**

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This document is in response to the paper Towards a European Career Framework for Researchers which was discussed at the Steering Group on Human Resources and Mobility (SGHRM), Skills WG meeting on July 9th in the European Commission.

Eurodoc comments:

- We are pleased to see that doctorate candidates are listed as researchers, on a clear career path.
- Eurodoc started a similar initiative in 2006 in a policy paper entitled Recommendations for the Organisation of Core Research Career Structures in Academia (25. 01. 2006). Though this paper was restricted to academia it already illuminated the path discussed here.
- The skills in question can be difficult to evaluate, though this difficulty should not hamper the need to realise such an evaluation. How shall it be determined when a researcher advances from one position to another?
- "Publishable quality" research is difficult to ascertain without the research actually having been published.
- In some fields (e. g. scientific experiments) it is more difficult to publish during the early phases of the research. Career measurements other than publications are important. Therefore, other activities like industry work and articles in newspapers and other non-academic publications should be credited, as these activities contribute to advancing public knowledge rather than simply that within the academic community.
- In the "star researcher" category it is the first place that interdisciplinary research comes into the equation, yet we actively involve a number of new doctoral candidates in a variety of interdisciplinary research projects. We suggest rephrasing the requirements.
- It should be noted that some researchers in some disciplines, as they advance in their careers, merely

manage projects and do not perform actual research themselves. Following that, some leading researchers may publish less than established or younger researchers. Furthermore, it should be noted that these categories are not to be fixed, as some researchers can lose contact with developments, due to concentrating on other issues such as appointments to the position of rector or dean. As such, some researchers may not be able to be considered "leading" anymore and could regress accordingly.

Eurodoc recommendations:

1. To support researchers in training, new doctoral candidates or early career research assistants in such a manner so that they will have paid positions with the security and benefits that can be reasonably expected.
2. Additions and changes to the categories:
 - **New Researcher** – doctoral candidates and other young scientists in their early career years setting up their own research framework, as well as those engaged in interdisciplinary research.
 - **Recognised Researcher** – doctoral candidates and other young scientists already with some publications and actively contributing knowledge to conferences and their research environment, as well as helping to formulate new interdisciplinary research frameworks.
 - **Established Researcher** – someone who has begun taking leading roles in research projects and has the ability to initiate new research projects, attract funding, etc. This would include academics but could also include post-doctoral researchers with some senior level of experience. Publications and also demonstration of leading research projects and their output puts researchers into this category. Some sort of accreditation/professional registration would be needed to help identify such researchers.

- **Leading Researcher** – the same as “established researcher” but would also know how to handle large projects and a role as leader of a large number of researchers. A head of a research department is an example of this type of researcher.
- **Star Researcher** – researchers who pioneer new ventures such as spin-off companies or large international research networks.

Eurodoc

The career development workgroup

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Contact the workgroup and the workgroup coordinator

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